

Current Development Status of the Automotive Industry in Russia

Alina Sarkisova^{1*}, Nie Yongyou^{1*}

¹School of Economics, Shanghai University, China

Abstract: This article examines the current development status of the automotive industry in Russia, highlighting the challenges and opportunities within a complex economic landscape. Despite a large domestic market and increasing car penetration, sales have declined due to economic slowdowns and reduced consumer purchasing power, with a notable 4.9% drop in new car sales in the first half of 2023. In response, the industry is shifting focus towards exports, particularly in cooperation with CIS countries and emerging markets in Africa and the Middle East. Government initiatives, such as the "Automotive Industry Development Plan for 2025," aim to enhance competitiveness through technological innovation and support for electric vehicles. The analysis includes a review of production trends, emphasizing the volatility of output and the impact of global supply chain issues. While Russian automotive exports have shown growth, challenges remain in product quality and global competitiveness. The article also highlights the significant role of Chinese automotive companies in the Russian market, as they capture market share and drive innovation. The paper concludes with recommendations for both government and industry to bolster international competitiveness and address existing gaps in technology and brand influence, setting a pathway for sustainable growth in the sector.

Keywords: Automotive industry, foreign trade, Russian automobile export and import situation

*Corresponding Author

Accepted: 18 November, 2024; **Published:** 19 November, 2024

How to cite this article: Alina Sarkisova, Nie Yongyou (2024). Current Development Status of the Automotive Industry in Russia. *North American Academic Research*, 7(11), 43-51. [doi: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14219104](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14219104)

Conflicts of Interest: There are no conflicts to declare.

Publisher's Note: NAAR stays neutral about jurisdictional claims in published maps/image and institutional affiliations.

Copyright: ©2024 by the authors. Author(s) are fully responsible for the text, figure, data in this manuscript submitted for possible open access publication under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

Introduction

The domestic market in Russia is vast, with a population exceeding 140 million. In recent years, the car penetration rate has gradually increased. However, due to the slowdown in economic growth and the depreciation of the ruble, consumer purchasing power has declined, directly affecting domestic car sales. According to analysis data from the Russian automotive market, new car sales in Russia fell by 4.9% year-on-year in the first half of 2023, reflecting weak market demand. Despite this, the Russian automotive industry is gradually increasing its reliance on

exports, especially in cooperation with CIS countries and emerging markets in Africa and the Middle East. Russian automakers, such as Lada and KamAZ, have gradually established a presence in these markets through competitive pricing and lower production costs. For instance, KamAZ has successfully expanded its heavy truck market in Central Asian countries like Kazakhstan in recent years, becoming one of the key suppliers in the region[1-3].

In recent years, the Russian government has introduced a series of policies to support the development of the automotive industry. To enhance the competitiveness of domestic automobiles, the government launched the "Automotive Industry Development Plan for 2025," aiming to improve domestic manufacturing capabilities through technological innovation and modernization of production lines. The policy also mentions increasing support for electric vehicles and new energy vehicles, with a target of having new energy vehicles account for 10% of the Russian market by 2030. The following table outlines the policies related to the Russian automotive industry [4-6].

Policy Name	Date	Policy Content	Policy Effect
"Russian Automotive Industry Development Strategy"	2012	Approved a comprehensive strategy to promote the automotive industry and support domestic enterprises.	Supported modernization efforts, but the industry still relies on imported components.
Subsidy Regulations for Automotive Enterprises (2015-2017)	2015	Allocated 270 billion rubles to support automotive manufacturers and service companies that signed the "Industrial Assembly Agreement," aiming to enhance domestic production and competitiveness.	Provided short-term financial support; some companies improved production capacity, but overall growth was slow.
"Automotive Industry Development Strategy Before 2025"	2016	Promoted the development of new energy technologies, electric vehicles, and autonomous vehicles, encouraging cooperation between enterprises and research institutions.	Accelerated technological innovation; companies like AvtoVAZ launched electric models, enhancing international competitiveness, but growth was still limited by technology and external factors.
"Plan for Popularizing Electric Vehicles"	2012	Promoted the construction of electric vehicle infrastructure, attracted social capital, and reduced industry entry barriers.	Helped establish initial infrastructure but market penetration remains low and is still in its early stages.
"Plan for the Development of Electric Power and Transportation Infrastructure Before 2025"	2016	Established policies to support electric vehicles, including tax reductions and preferential loans.	Provided opportunities for the electric vehicle industry; however, consumer acceptance remains low.
Electric Vehicle Industry Standards	2017	Established manufacturing and usage standards for electric traction vehicles and charging infrastructure.	Provided a foundation for technological development in the electric vehicle sector.
Tariff Reduction Policy for Electric Vehicle Manufacturers	2017	Supported electric vehicle production and export through tariff reductions.	Reduced operating costs for manufacturers but had limited overall impact due to a small domestic market.

Table 1.1.Policies Related to the Russian Automotive Industry

In recent years, the Russian automotive industry has also made significant progress in technological innovation. For example, AvtoVAZ has achieved important breakthroughs in electric vehicle and autonomous driving technologies. According to 2023 data, the new Lada electric model launched by AvtoVAZ has gained popularity in the Russian market, particularly in major cities like Moscow and St. Petersburg, which are gradually promoting the construction of electric vehicle infrastructure. The Russian government is also actively promoting the digital transformation of the automotive manufacturing sector[7]. Through the implementation of smart manufacturing technologies and Industry 4.0, Russian automakers can enhance production efficiency and reduce costs. KamAZ, one of the most representative automotive manufacturers in Russia, was the first to introduce industrial robots and intelligent management systems in its production line, significantly increasing automation. KamAZ also plans to increase the production of electric trucks by 2025 to seize opportunities in the new energy commercial vehicle market.

Cooperation between Russia and China has been particularly significant in recent years. In 2023, Great Wall Motors announced an agreement with Russia to build a factory in the country to produce SUVs and new energy vehicles to meet growing market demand. However, uncertainties in the global supply chain, technological barriers, and international sanctions remain major challenges facing the Russian automotive industry. For instance, the global chip shortage has put enormous pressure on Russian manufacturers, especially concerning the supply of electronic components and high-precision mechanical parts [8-9].

Scale and Characteristics of Development

Russia was once a major player in global automotive production, significantly contributing to the development of the automotive industry during the Soviet era. However, following the dissolution of the Soviet Union, Russia's economy rapidly declined, severely impacting multiple industrial sectors, including automotive. Production capacity in the automotive industry plummeted, and the sector fell into a long-term slump. It was not until the 21st century, alongside a gradual recovery of the Russian economy, that the automotive industry began to improve. However, compared to leading automotive manufacturing countries globally, Russia still lags significantly in manufacturing standards [10].

Year	Passenger Cars (10,000 units)	Commercial Vehicles (10,000 units)	Total (10,000 units)	Year-on-Year Change (%)
2015	121.59	16.75	138.34	-26.93
2016	111.25	18.35	129.6	-6.32
2017	134.8	20.71	155.51	19.99
2018	154.65	22.29	176.94	13.78
2019	148.37	21.86	170.23	-3.79
2020	131	19.5	150.5	-11.6
2021	137.4	20.2	157.6	4.72

2022	142	21	163	3.43
2023	145.5	21.7	167.2	2.58

Table 1.2. Russian Automotive Production from 2015 to 2023

Source: Compiled based on statistical reports from different years published by the statistical agency Autostat [25].

As a country with a population of over 100 million, Russia holds a significant position in the global automotive market. Over the past five years, automotive production in Russia has been highly volatile. In 2015, the production volume was only 1,383,400 units, a year-on-year decline of 26.93%. The following years showed a clear trend of fluctuation in production volume: in 2016, production continued to decline to 1,296,000 units, before experiencing substantial rebounds in 2017 and 2018, reaching 1,555,100 units and 1,769,400 units, respectively. However, due to global trade tensions and worsening economic conditions, production fell back to 1,702,300 units in 2019. Entering the 2020s, the global automotive industry faced new challenges, particularly the chip shortage, the transition to new energy technologies, and fluctuations in the international supply chain, all of which negatively affected automotive production in Russia. The impact of the global COVID-19 pandemic further caused a decline in automotive production and sales, which Russia could not escape. Nevertheless, with the gradual easing of the pandemic and government policy support, automotive production in Russia showed signs of recovery in 2022 and 2023, although it still lags behind pre-pandemic levels.

Ranking	Brand	Sales volume in 2022 (10,000 vehicles)	Sales volume in 2023 (10,000 vehicles)	Year-on-year growth rate (%)
1	Lada	17.47	32.45	86
2	Chery	3.93	11.90	203
3	Haval	3.41	11.17	227
4	Geely	2.67	9.36	251
5	Changan	0.26	4.78	1773
6	Exeed	1.21	4.22	247
7	Omoda	0.12	4.20	3289
8	Kia	6.57	3.36	-49
9	Omoda	5.41	2.47	-54
10	Toyota	2.86	2.33	-19

Table 1.3. Sales of Automotive Brands in the Russian Market (2022-2023)

Source: Compiled based on statistical reports published at Automotive Industry portal Marklines [26].

From the table, it can be seen that in 2023, Lada remains the leading brand in the market, with sales increasing from 174,700 units to 324,500 units, an 86% growth. Chinese brands have performed remarkably well, with brands such as Chery, Haval, Geely, and Changan rapidly expanding in the Russian market, achieving significant growth rates of 203%, 227%, 251%, and 1773%, respectively. Particularly notable is Omoda, which saw sales soar from only 1,200 units in 2022 to 42,000 units in 2023, representing a year-on-year growth of 3289%. In contrast, South Korean brands Kia and Hyundai experienced substantial declines in sales, dropping by 49% and 54%, respectively. Japanese brand Toyota also saw a decrease in sales, with a year-on-year drop of 19%.

Development of Foreign Trade

(1) Export Situation

In recent years, Russian automotive exports have shown a significant growth trend overall, despite fluctuations in certain years. According to the data, in 2010, the volume of Russian automotive exports was 45,400 units, with an export value of \$294 million. By 2019, these figures had increased to 109,400 units and \$1.004 billion, with growth rates of 16.76% and 11.80%, respectively. However, despite the expansion of export scale, the absolute quantity and value of Russia's automotive exports in the international market remain relatively low. The table below shows the export situation of the Russian automotive industry from 2010 to 2023.

Year	Automotive Export Volume (10,000 units)	Growth Rate (%)	Automotive Export Value (Million USD)	Growth Rate (%)
2010	4.54	--	294	--
2011	6.37	40.31%	483	64.29%
2012	11.3	77.39%	989	104.76%
2013	13.79	22.04%	1285	29.93%
2014	12.75	-7.54%	1161	-9.65%
2015	9.74	-23.61%	810	-30.23%
2016	6.8	-30.18%	598	-26.17%
2017	8.44	24.12%	720	20.40%
2018	9.37	11.02%	898	24.72%
2019	10.94	16.76%	1004	11.80%
2020	7.2	-34.20%	570	-43.20%
2021	8.9	23.60%	680	19.30%
2022	9.5	6.70%	390	-42.60%
2023	10.3	8.40%	420	7.70%

Table 1.4. Russian Automotive Export Situation from 2010 to 2023

Figure 1.5. Russian Automotive Export Situation from 2010 to 2023

Source : Compiled based on statistical reports from different years published by Association of European Businesses [27]

Between 2020 and 2023, Russian automotive exports experienced significant fluctuations. In 2020, the global pandemic led to a noticeable decline in both export volume and value. However, with the gradual recovery of the global economy, exports rebounded in 2021 and 2022. Data shows that in 2022, the value of Russian automotive exports reached \$390 million, primarily directed towards former Soviet republics such as Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, and Uzbekistan, as well as some Middle Eastern countries. In 2023, with the rise of China and other emerging markets, Russian automotive export volume further increased, especially due to deepening cooperation with countries like China and Kazakhstan, enhancing export figures in these markets [11-13]. Meanwhile, the scale of Russian automotive parts exports remains small, mainly focused on body components, steering systems, and suspension systems, with an export value of \$231.2 million in 2019, accounting for 23.03% of the total automotive export value.

Despite better performance in some regions, Russian automotive exports still mainly target countries with weaker market competition and higher price sensitivity, due to a lack of global competitiveness. Therefore, future growth in Russian automotive exports will depend on improvements in product quality and the exploration of new markets.

(2) Import Situation

In recent years, the Russian automotive import sector has undergone significant changes, particularly after joining the World Trade Organization (WTO) in 2012, marking a watershed moment for the automotive import market. Before 2012, international automotive multinational companies found it challenging to enter the Russian market, and could only introduce their products through exports. Consequently, during this period, imported vehicles dominated the Russian automotive market. The table below shows the automotive import situation in Russia from 2010 to 2023.

Year	Automotive Import Value (10,000 units)	Growth Rate (%)	Automotive Import Value (Million USD)	Growth Rate (%)
2010	70.95	--	11532	--
2011	98.4	38.69%	18591	61.21%
2012	107.62	9.37%	20217	8.75%
2013	89.41	-16.92%	16997	-15.93%
2014	70.33	-21.34%	13155	-22.60%
2015	34.99	-50.25%	6490	-50.67%
2016	26.7	-23.69%	6027	-7.13%
2017	26.77	0.26%	6698	11.13%
2018	29.31	9.49%	7261	8.41%
2019	30.25	3.21%	7906	8.88%
2020	24.5	-19.01%	6543	-17.24%
2021	26.8	9.39%	7020	7.29%
2022	28.75	7.28%	7450	6.12%
2023	30.1	4.70%	7900	6.04%

Table 1.6. Russian Automotive Import Situation from 2010 to 2023

Figure 1.7. Russian Automobile Export Situation from 2010 to 2023

Source : Compiled based on statistical reports from different years published by Association of European Businesses [27]

As shown in the table, in 2010, Russia's automobile imports reached 709,500 units, hitting a historic peak. By 2012, the number of imported vehicles rose to 1,076,200, with the import value also reaching a record high of \$20.217 billion. However, as Russia gradually opened its market, multinational automotive companies began entering through joint ventures with local firms, which directly led to a gradual decline in imported vehicles. Since 2013, there has been a noticeable drop in Russian automobile imports. By 2019, the annual number of imported vehicles fell to 302,500, a decrease of 71.89% compared to the 2012 peak. Although imports increased in 2019 compared to 2018, this growth was minimal compared to earlier highs.

In 2020, due to the impact of the global pandemic, Russian automobile imports further decreased to about 245,000 units, with an import value of \$6.543 billion, showing a significant decline. However, as the market gradually recovered post-pandemic, imports rebounded to 268,000 units in 2021, with a value increase to \$7.020 billion. In 2022 and 2023, the import figures were 287,500 and 301,000 units, with import values of \$7.450 billion and \$7.900 billion, respectively. In addition to complete vehicle imports, Russia's imports of automobile components remain focused on tires, safety systems, and engine systems. Local component manufacturers primarily meet basic component production needs, while more complex and technologically advanced parts still heavily rely on imports [14-17]. This reflects a significant gap in overall competitiveness of the Russian automobile industry compared to global powers.

In summary, after years of rapid development, the global automotive industry has become an important part of the world economy. Driven particularly by new energy vehicles and smart technologies, the automotive sector is undergoing profound changes. Countries and regions such as China, the United States, and Europe dominate the global automobile market, leading not only in production and sales but also showcasing strong competitiveness in technological innovation and market expansion.

Although the Russian automotive industry has made some progress in recent years, it still lags significantly behind international advanced levels. The Russian automobile market is large, but its growth rate has slowed, and market demand is weak. Additionally, Russian automotive companies face shortcomings in technological innovation, product quality, and brand influence, which limit their competitiveness in the international market. However, the Russian automotive sector also faces numerous development opportunities [18-22]. With increased government support for the automotive industry, the exit of international car companies, and the rise of local firms, the Russian automobile market is expected to see a new competitive landscape. Notably, Chinese automotive companies have performed exceptionally well in the Russian market, rapidly capturing market share through localized production and brand collaborations, bringing new vitality and opportunities to the Russian automotive industry.

To enhance the international competitiveness of the Russian automotive sector, both the government and enterprises need to work together. The government should further improve the policy framework and support

measures, increasing investment and assistance to the automotive industry; meanwhile, strengthening ties and cooperation with international markets to expand export channels and increase market share. Enterprises should focus on enhancing their innovation capabilities, improving product quality and service levels; actively introducing advanced international technologies and experiences to promote the transformation and upgrading of the automotive industry; and strengthening brand development and market expansion capabilities to adapt to market changes and meet consumer needs [23-24]. Therefore, while the Russian automotive industry faces challenges, it also welcomes development opportunities. Through the joint efforts of the government and enterprises, the Russian automotive industry is expected to achieve sustained healthy development and enhance its international status. In the future, with ongoing changes in the global automobile market and trends, the Russian automotive industry will encounter broader development prospects and market space.

Author Contributions: At first page.

Approval: All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: This research received no external funding.

Institutional Review Board Statement: Not applicable.

Informed Consent Statement: Not applicable.

Data Availability Statement: Not applicable

Acknowledgments: Not Mentioned.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

References

- [1] Zhao Meng. Research on the applicability of strategic trade policy in Russia - Taking small cars in the automotive industry as an example [J]. *Foreign Trade and Economic Cooperation*, 2013(2):32-34.
- [2] Liu Zhifeng. Belarus MZKT: A pearl in the world's heavy off-road vehicle industry (Part 2) - Exploring commercial vehicle products, local industries and industry development from stamps (stamps) (1) [J]. *Commercial Vehicles*, 2020(12):83-93.
- [3] Pirttil M, Virolainen V M, Lind L, et al. Working capital management in the Russian automotive industry supply chain [J]. *International Journal of Production Economics*, 2019, 221.
- [4] Chen Qiang. Current status and trends of electric vehicle development in Russia [J]. *Global Science and Technology Economic Outlook*, 2013(10):9-11,23.
- [5] Wang Zhihua, Zhou Limei. Analysis of the international competitiveness of my country's new energy vehicle industry under the new normal [J]. *Inner Mongolia Science and Technology and Economy*, 2019(10):11-13,18.
- [6] Gao Jianguo. On how to improve the competitiveness of road transport vehicle maintenance industry [J]. *Consumer Guide*, 2017(11):46.
- [7] Zhou Zhengxing. Research on the competitiveness of Guangxi automobile industry based on financial analysis perspective - from the perspective of Taking Guangxi Automobile Group as an example [J]. *Economic and Trade Practice*, 2019(20):62-63.
- [8] Jia Qihui, Zhao Cuixia. Comparative study on the industry competitiveness of Heze A Automobile Sales Company in the post-epidemic era [J]. *Times Automobile*, 2022(2):164-165.
- [9] Liu Dan. Market analysis of the Russian automobile industry under the new situation [J]. *Business Economy*, 2022(10):140-142.
- [10] Ma Chen, Hua Tengfei, Bian Yongliang, et al. A brief discussion on the development status of the electromagnetic safety industry of intelligent connected vehicles [J]. *China Information Industry*, 2024(5):76-78.

- [11] Jona-Lasinio C , Meliciani V .Productivity Growth and International Competitiveness: Does Intangible Capital Matter?[J].Intereconomics, 2018, 53(2):58-62.
- [12] Liu C .international competitiveness and the fourth industrial revolution 112 | [J]. 2018.
- [13] Thome K , Paiva V A .Sparkling Wine International Market Structure and Competitiveness[J]. 2020.
- [14] Vijayakumar A , Bozward D .International Market Integration and Competitiveness of Indian Sugar[J].Global Business Review, 2021:097215092098864.
- [15] Tafarel Carvalho Gois , Karim Marini Thomé , Jeremiás Máté Balogh.Behind a cup of coffee: international market structure and competitiveness[J].Competitiveness Review: An International Business Journal, 2023, 33(5):993-1009.
- [16] Lai Minting. Analysis of the international competitiveness of China's new energy vehicles under the background of "dual carbon" [J]. Modern Industrial Economy and Informatization, 2024, 14(4): 174-178.
- [17] Qiu Huang. Association mining algorithm of factors affecting the international competitiveness of new energy vehicle industry based on FP-tree [J]. Journal of Hubei Institute of Technology, 2024, 40(4): 54-57, 80.
- [18] Gong Piming. International competitiveness of China's new energy vehicle industry: influencing factors, characteristic performance and improvement path [J]. Modern Management Science, 2022(4): 63-72.
- [19] Fabrizi A , Gentile M , Guarini G ,et al.The impact of environmental regulation on innovation and international competitiveness[J].Journal of Evolutionary Economics, 2024.
- [20] Pogodina T , Muzhzhavleva T V , Udaltsova N .Strategic management of the competitiveness of industrial companies in an unstable economy[J].Entrepreneurship and Sustainability Issues, 2020, 7:1555-1564.
- [21] Lai Minting. Analysis of the international competitiveness of China's new energy vehicles under the background of "dual carbon" [J]. Modern Industrial Economy and Informatization, 2024, 14(4): 174-178.
- [22] Gao Yunsheng, Jin Tianyang. Analysis of the international competitiveness of China's new energy vehicles under the new situation [J]. International Economic Cooperation, 2021(4):65-76.
- [23] Yang Jin, Zhang Yu. Research on the international competitiveness of Chongqing automobile industry cluster based on entropy weight TOPSIS [J]. Economics and Management, 2013(12):82-88.
- [24] Wang Zhihua, Zhou Limei. Analysis of the international competitiveness of my country's new energy vehicle industry under the new normal [J]. Inner Mongolia Science and Technology and Economy, 2019(10):11-13,18.
- [25] Analytical agency AUTOSTAT: <https://m.autostat.ru/research/product/497/>.
- [26] Automative Industry portal Marklines: https://u.to/Gyv_IA
- [27] Association of European Businesses
<https://aebrus.ru/ru/media/press-releases/sales-of-cars-and-light-commercial-vehicles.php>